

Business Process Management Practices in a South African State-Owned Enterprise

Lumka T.P. Salamntu^{0000-0001-6438-809X} and Lisa F. Seymour⁰⁰⁰⁰⁻⁰⁰⁰¹⁻⁶⁷⁰⁴⁻⁰⁰²¹

CITANDA, University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa
slmtha004@myuct.ac.za

Abstract. Business Process Management (BPM) is a methodology for managing and optimising business processes. South African State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs) have adopted BPM, though the extent of its implementation varies. This study aims to describe the BPM practices within a South African SOE through an interpretive case study. In the literature review, three models were compared to identify BPM practices and a comprehensive BPM practice model was first derived. In the SOE case, the BPM practices reveal that BPM was ICT-driven and that the integration of BPM into the organisation's strategy had limited focus. This study contributes to BPM literature by highlighting BPM practices within a South African SOE, an area that has received limited attention. The derived comprehensive BPM model can serve as a guide when implementing BPM in SOEs.

Keywords: Business Process Management Practices, Business Process Management Lifecycle, South Africa, State-Owned Enterprises.

1 Introduction

State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs) worldwide are struggling with ineffective and inefficient business operations [1]. To address this issue, they have invested in various initiatives, with Business Process Management (BPM) among the key approaches adopted. BPM is a management approach that offers means to manage and optimise business processes and has a positive influence on organisational performance [2, 3]. BPM has been known to improve organisational performance [3]. BPM, as defined by scholars, is a multidisciplinary concept that has matured with a well-established set of principles, methods and tools for improving business processes [4]. The earliest forms of BPM can be traced back to the Industrial Revolution [5] and its current role in new technologies and trends. The use of technological innovation elevated the discipline [6]. Effective BPM can streamline and improve service delivery, which is crucial for an organisation to thrive, and can also facilitate better alignment between business processes and corporate strategy [7, 8]. In South Africa, SOEs are investing a substantial amount of money in BPM projects to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of processes. SOEs are public organisations that are partially or fully owned by the government and are significantly involved in the global economy [9]. Despite the SOEs adopting BPM, it is not publicly known what BPM practices are executed. Hence, this study seeks to describe BPM practices in a South African SOE, and the research question is: How is Business Process Management practiced in a South African SOE? To achieve the objective and answer the question, a comprehensive BPM lifecycle

model is first derived from the literature, providing a structure for describing BPM practices. This paper is structured as follows: it outlines the process taken to review the literature, and the three studied BPM lifecycle models are presented in the subsequent section. This is followed by the methodology. Finally, the findings and discussion are presented, and the conclusion is outlined.

2 Literature Review

This study followed the literature review method as suggested by Wolfswinkel et al., [10], consisting of five stages namely: define, search, select, analyse and present. The first stage involves defining the search strategy and outlining the specification of what will be searched, where and how [11]. All the relevant data about this study was identified. The search stage allowed for the actual search to be conducted, and this was done using four databases namely: Google Scholar, Web of Science, EBSCOhost and Scopus. These databases were chosen because they offer a wide range of literature, including high-quality peer-reviewed scholarly journals, and are high-impact databases with cited literature across disciplines. The search string used was “Business Process Management lifecycle” OR “Business Process Management Practices” AND “State-Owned Enterprises”. The same search string was applied across the four selected databases. Papers written in the English language and peer-reviewed between 2019 and 2025 were evaluated. The focus was on BPM practices in South African SOEs. While the select stage was used to screen publications that focused on BPM practices or the BPM lifecycle. The search criteria yielded 30 publications from Google Scholar, 124 from Web of Science, 100 from EBSCOhost, and 92 from Scopus. Duplicates were removed using matches on the digital object identifier reference. The selection stage identified publications that did not meet the inclusion criteria based on their titles and abstracts and were removed. The remaining articles were screened by reviewing their full text. A total of 15 publications across the four databases remained for analysis as they were most relevant in this study. In the analysis stage, the articles were read several times. Sentences and paragraphs that were relevant to answer the research question were noted. This process was repeated.

A BPM lifecycle model systematises the steps and activities involved in conducting BPM projects [12]. Several BPM lifecycle models include phases or practices that do not run in a linear sequence with others. This leads to organisations practicing BPM in various ways [13, 14]. Consequently, this can lead to confusion among practitioners [15]. This study compared and consolidated three BPM lifecycle models. These models were selected due to their relevance in providing the most appropriate lens for describing BPM practices. Firstly, the BPM lifecycle model developed by Dumas et al. [4] which will be referred to as the Dumas et al model. The second model, developed by Harmon [16], is referred to as the BPTrends model. The third model, introduced by the Department of Public Service and Administration (DPSA) [17], was selected for its contextual relevance to South African government entities and is referred to as the DPSA model. Other models focused on BPM systems, workflow management and process mining which was outside the scope of this study. The next sections describe the three selected models.

2.1 The Dumas et al Model

The Dumas et al model as shown in **Fig. 1**, comprises six phases with each phase serving a distinct role. This model proposes the identification of processes, emphasises continuous improvement and integration of business processes. (1) Process identification refers to management activities that define a set of business processes and establish an explicit criterion for selecting specific processes for improvement. (2) The second phase, named process discovery, involves the creation of 'As-Is' process model and the generation of a comprehensive business process description report. (3) The process analysis phase is responsible for identifying and analysing weaknesses and bottlenecks found in the 'As Is' process models. (4) The process redesign phase uses insights from the previous phase to model more efficient and effective business processes, referred to as a 'To Be' process model. (5) The process implementation translates the 'To Be' process model into a state that can be monitored. Lastly, (6) the process monitoring phase ensures that the implemented 'To Be' process model adheres to performance targets and conform to objectives. Any deviation from the organisational goals triggers an iteration of the lifecycle.

Fig.1. The Dumas et al Model [3]

2.2 The BPTrends Model

The six-stage BPTrends by Harmon [16] is shown in **Fig.2**, and it suggests that the first step is (1) the corporate process management which is to determine the corporate strategy and identify business processes that will be improved within the organisation. Following this is (2) the necessity to understand the project and define its scope. The BPM project is initiated upon approval, triggering (3) the process analysis phase, which identifies the 'As Is' processes. Any deficiencies in the 'As Is' processes are identified. (4) the process redesign phase improves the identified deficiencies in the 'As Is' state, and a fully documented 'To Be' process model is produced. (5) The implementation phase ensures that the new software used for 'To Be' processes is created and tested, and users are trained. (6) The last phase is used to manage the 'To Be' processes and it is called rollout redesigned processes.

Fig. 2. The BPTrends Model [16]

2.3 The DPSA Model

The DPSA model was primarily developed for government entities and comprises six phases, as illustrated in Fig.3. The first phase prepares and sensitises the top management about the BPM project. In the second phase, the ‘As Is’ processes are analysed and documented to ensure that the business process description report is established. Subsequently, the business process approach is determined, and the ‘To Be’ process model is designed and implemented. The last phase ensures that the processes are maintained. This study considered this model since it fits the current context well. In this model, phase 3 was the only phase identified as unique and critical for describing BPM practices, which was not included in the other two models.

Fig. 3. The DPSA Model [17]

2.4 The Comprehensive BPM Practice Model

The Comprehensive BPM practice model was derived from three models, highlighting their differences and similarities, as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The Comprehensive BPM Practice Model

The DPSA model addresses preparation and activation during the first phase, as well as the phase that determines the improvement approach, unlike the other two models. The DPSA model does not identify the need for corporate process management. However, there are similar practices across the three models, such as process analysis, ‘To Be’ processes, process implementation, and process monitoring and control. The integration of the three models yields a more comprehensive BPM practice model, as it encompasses the most critical phases from multiple models rather than relying solely on a single model. This model can be validated in future studies, particularly in South African SOEs, as it aims to describe BPM practices in SOEs.

3 Method

This study seeks to describe the BPM practices within a South African SOE. According to a set of principles concerning the views of the world from which research is conducted, interpretivism claims that individuals have their own understanding of reality and perceptions [18]. Since BPM practices are best understood from the individual's perspective, an interpretivist stance was most suitable. The abductive approach allows for new insight that might not be known. Given that BPM practices are

not well understood from a South African SOE perspective, an abductive approach was utilised to better understand them. The three BPM lifecycle models were selected to gain a broad understanding of BPM practices. [19] argue that studies relying on abduction can modify the original framework(s) based on empirical findings and theoretical insights gained.

Drawing on Dubois et al. [19] argument that the abductive approach allows for the modification of initial frameworks based on empirical insights. Each model underwent a thorough examination, and unique phases were identified, and overlapping phases were determined based on shared activities. This led to the phases being integrated into a comprehensive BPM practice model. This approach ensured that the consolidated model reflects a more holistic view of BPM practices. Thus, this study employed this model to understand the BPM practices in a South African SOE.

SOEs are established by the South African government to promote economic growth [20]. SOEs are formed to address market failures, deliver essential services to the public [21], and achieve lower costs for public goods and services [22]. Despite their critical role in South Africa, SOEs have struggled with continuous operational inefficiencies caused by inefficient business processes and outdated legacy systems. To resolve this, the SOEs have invested significantly in BPM projects, aiming to identify bottlenecks and eliminate redundant activities. The selected SOE was no exception. This study used one of the established South African SOEs, and it was purposively selected. The SOE was willing to participate in the study. This study used purposeful sampling, and fifteen participants were interviewed. Table 1 lists participants and their years of experience.

Table 1. Participants' role description and years of experience

Code	Rank	Experience
P1	<i>Business Process Analyst</i>	7 Years
P2	<i>Business Process Analyst</i>	7 Years
P3	<i>Project Manager</i>	16 Years
P4	<i>Senior Business Process Analyst</i>	9 Years
P5	<i>Senior Business Process Analyst</i>	10 Years
P6	<i>Programme Director</i>	15 Years
P7	<i>BPM Project Coordinator</i>	4 Years
P8	<i>Senior Business Process Analyst</i>	9 Years
P9	<i>Senior Process Engineer</i>	14 Years
P10	<i>Chief Information Officer</i>	30 Years
P11	<i>Senior Process Engineer</i>	15 Years
P12	<i>Project Manager</i>	35 Years
P13	<i>Programme Director</i>	27 Years
P14	<i>Quality Assurance Analyst</i>	14 Years
P15	<i>Project Manager</i>	26 Years

The researcher collected data through semi-structured interviews, and each interview was recorded with the participant's permission. The transcripts were coded and analysed before meeting with the next participant. A flexible approach to data collection was adopted, enabling the refinement of questions based on participant responses. This aligns with Charmaz's [23] perspective of adopting a more flexible approach to

data collection in the field. All fifteen participants were relevant and involved in the process of adopting BPM within the organisation, hence they were purposively selected for this study. Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the academic institution and the case. The participants ranged from Chief Information Officer, Project Manager, Senior Process Engineers, and others. Continuing beyond the 15 participants would have been redundant, as no new information emerged.

The coding process followed Charmaz's [23] approach. This involved a line-by-line examination of data to identify initial concepts, and incidents were compared. The practices described what was visible in the data. The coding was performed in NVivo [24]. The coding was structured based on the comprehensive BPM practice model. Some practices were more dominant in the SOE than others. However, each code will be explained in detail in the findings and discussion section.

4 Findings and Discussion

This study utilised the comprehensive BPM practice model as a lens to describe BPM practices within the case. This section presents the findings and discusses how BPM is practiced in the case.

4.1 Corporate Process Management

In the SOE, BPM did not appear to be aligned with the organisational strategy, and one participant said, "It's not focused on a direction or strategy where specifically BPM would follow" (P1). It is often difficult to understand a process or develop a system without understanding the existing processes. Hence, the Dumas et al and Harmon models recommend identifying processes when executing BPM-related projects. This phase not only supports the development of a process architecture but also establishes the BPM foundation. The SOE had no formal process architecture. Process identification practices appear limited to listing processes with common goals, "number of processes that need to speak to each other to arrive at a common goal" (P3). Initiatives adopted and executed outside the organisational strategy allow individuals to exercise autonomy, even when they contradict organisational goals. For instance, the lack of integrating BPM into the organisational strategy often leads to a lack of support from top management. "So, we do not have that control and that support from top management in the business units" (P1).

The individuals in the SOE were reported to be carrying out tasks however they see fit. "Like I said, they are doing things for the sake of doing them..." (P3). Due to a lack of strategic alignment, things are done ambiguously, as alluded by one of the participants, "Just that the way we do things...yho its wishy washy" (P1). To summarise, BPM lacks formal strategic governance, leading it to be viewed as an operational task rather than a strategic initiative. This also shows that BPM in the SOE was ICT-driven rather than top-management-driven, as it was not incorporated into the organisational strategy, thereby opening a loop for individuals to exercise autonomy.

4.2 Preparation and Action

Every organisation has a unique starting point for BPM, shaped by its business needs and culture. For instance, one business may need to automate processes where others require better traceability and performance measures. Regardless of where the business starts, it is often critical for businesses to understand the BPM projects and secure leadership buy-in. According to the DPSA model, it is crucial to secure leadership commitment and buy-in, and to conduct a stakeholder analysis from the outset. A lot was done in the SOE to ensure that people were made aware, and the top management was also informed about the BPM project. “People are made aware of it, especially at the top management level, to say this is what BPM is about” (P1). The top management level is made aware, and “BPM is also well understood, sponsored within the organisation” (P5).

The DPSA model also underscores the importance of stakeholder analysis during the preparation and activation phases. In the SOE, management, senior process engineers and business process analysts were among the stakeholders involved in the BPM project. Despite not having a BPM strategy, there were some engagements with various stakeholders. “But the engagements with the various stakeholders, you can see the excitement” (P2). Another participant mentioned that the organisation lacks tools to map processes to fulfil specific BPM objectives. “So, we need tooling and make sure that the tool that we use, for example, to map this process is uh proficient enough to be able to fulfil the need for our specific BPM objective” (P5).

To summarise, the top management and BPM professionals were involved in the BPM project. However, there are contradicting views pertaining to management embracing change brought about by the BPM project. Top management was involved because they embrace change, as explained by the participant, “and then there are those that do embrace change that want to improve the way they work, those that want to gain efficiencies” (P2). While some resist change. It was found that not everyone at the top management level embraces change, which explains the resistance.

4.3 Process Analysis

The process analysis phase represents how the business processes are currently executed in the organisation, and it identifies weaknesses in the process and determines their impact on business performance [4, 16, 17]. This is the first phase identified across the three models examined in this study. The analysts have identified that it takes 21 days to acquire goods and services, from the time goods and/or services are requested through invoice processing and payment. There were suggestions for better ways to work, some of which were accepted and others rejected. “The colleagues from Oracle are suggesting better ways of doing things, and some of them, uh, get accepted, some of them get rejected” (P2).

One participant mentioned that BPM has brought about improvements and, as a result, it is part of the performance scorecard. “So, shame there have been a number of improvements, and I think because it's part of our performance score cards to identify those on a daily basis and implement them” (P1). It was interesting to note that even though BPM was not part of the organisational strategy as suggested in the literature,

it was part of the strategic management implementation tools, which in the SOE was the performance scorecard.

Additionally, processes and standard operating procedures, or process description reports, for finance and procurement were documented in the SOE for automation purposes. “You document processes and standard procedures to be able to automate processes” (P5). The Business process analysts documented the processes; however, priority was given to the finance and procurement processes, representing support units within the organisation. “I think I don't know whether it's too early for me to make this example. But uh you are aware that we did map some processes for procurement and finance” (P2). This shows that support processes, which are utilised daily within the organisation, were prioritised.

In the SOE, the adoption of BPM was found to be poor and still dependent on external consultants. There was no document outlining BPM. “We are still not aware, or I'm not sure if that's the correct word” (P1). “So, in the greater scheme of things, the adoption of BPM is actually quite bad, quite poor in that it is still dependent on external consultants” (P5). “People focus on their processes and what they do, not necessarily what they hand over to other people” (P1). “After being here for quite a number of years, so there is no literature, there's no book that I can refer you to or document that I can refer you to that actually outlines any business process management” (P3). To summarise, the SOE's process analysis phase has enabled the organisation to analyse its processes and identify several weaknesses. This phase was more often executed in the SOE, with more references than other phases.

4.4 Determine Improvement Approach

The determine improvement approach phase allows organisations to determine which business process approach will be utilised in the BPM project. For instance, when adopting BPM, this kind of practice suggests what to focus on when executing a BPM initiative, which can either be an incremental improvement approach or a redesign approach. However, it is essential for the organisation to select an approach that best suits its needs and culture [17]. The SOE adopted an incremental improvement approach rather than a redesign approach. One participant mentioned that BPM in the SOE was adopted to improve processes. “So basically, the project was around a business process improvement for the organisation” (P1).

A BPM improvement approach is chosen when an organisation wants to make the existing processes more efficient and effective. It was found that the procurement process in the SOE was lengthy and needed to be improved, rather than redesigned. “...Which then means that the entire procurement process itself is very lengthy. It is very cumbersome, but we are able to shorten it, and the SOE has improved greatly in terms of streamlining the systems” (P3). In summary, the SOE practiced a BPM improvement approach with the goal of improving its existing processes rather than mapping the processes from scratch. This was done because it was believed that the processes were not broken but needed some improvements; hence, the SOE did not follow the redesign approach.

4.5 Design “To Be” Processes

The design “To Be” process phase ensures that the “As Is” processes are improved and modelled into a “To Be” process model, which can be automated and used by the organisation. This practice was also common across the three models. Every activity in the “To Be” process should add value, be adequate, have sufficient resources and be used as the basis for implementation. Numerous changes and improvements have been made to the processes to ensure that the process flows smoothly in the SOE. One participant mentioned that they have removed all bottlenecks and time-wasting activities from their processes. “Oh, shame there have been a number of improvements” (P1). The other participant said, “But there are those processes that actually, uh, through BPM were improved” (P2). In the SOE, BPM was utilised to make changes and improvements. “So, there are a few changes, there are a few improvements” (P2). In summary, BPM in the SOE has helped identify bottlenecks and time-consuming activities. The finance and procurement processes have undergone significant improvements.

4.6 Process Implementation

The process implementation involves providing the information systems infrastructure for running the ‘To Be’ processes, with personnel trained on how the newly developed processes are intended to operate. During this phase, processes are automated and transformed, and people are trained. In the SOE, some processes were stated to have been automated, such as the billing and invoice approval processes. According to P3, invoices are now signed electronically. “Yes, yes, I approve. Invoices, here. [shows his smart phone]. If somebody needs to sign a document, it goes on e-signature” (P3). While another participant said, “And then there are lots of processes that we have automated. Like the billing process” (P1). The participants mentioned that many processes people were working on were automated. Also, manual processes were automated. “So that has been automated and I think there are a lot of processes that people were working on that have been automated” (P1). “Um, and also the fact that uh, some of them that were manual processes have now been automated” (P2).

In summary, the BPM project facilitated the automation of certain processes, enabling some approvals to be completed electronically. The billing process is among those automated. The literature emphasises the need for training; it was mentioned in the SOE that only people who were involved in documenting and analysing the processes were trained. “You know the people who make up the team to document processes, to analyse processes, process data, etc., right, are to have the necessary skills, are trained” (P5). Therefore, training was limited to the BPM team, which contradicts the BPM goal.

4.7 Process Monitoring and Control

The process monitoring and control phase provides insights into the process's conformance and performance. If the process's conformance and performance do not align with organisational goals or key performance indicators, the cycle returns to the

prepare and activation phase. It is uncommon for all phases to be executed in a strictly sequential manner. Process monitoring and control were among the practices not fully executed in the SOE, due to the lack of not incorporating BPM into the organisational strategy. In the SOE, the performance of processes was not clearly monitored, and there was a lack of control over how processes operate. Despite some participants mentioning that the organisation sees the benefits of the improved processes, in that processes are now more efficient and effective, and that the various departments have improved drastically. Some of the participants said, “they are seeing the benefits of the processes that were improved” (P2). “But then there are specific departments or business units which have improved drastically on this” (P5).

To summarise, although processes were not fully monitored and controlled effectively, some processes were improved, and certain business units were reported to have undergone significant improvements. The monitoring of processes is intended to track deviations from the expected performance; however, in the SOE, BPM was practiced outside the organisational strategy, “Ok, I also don’t think there is a BPM strategy (P7)”. Not having BPM incorporated in the organisational strategy makes it difficult to explicitly identify deviations against a set of expected performance measures.

5 Conclusion

The goal of this paper was to describe BPM practices in a South African SOE. The literature review contrasted three BPM lifecycle models and derived a comprehensive model that was used to theme BPM practices. The case study contrasted these literature practices with those in the South African SOE. It was found that not all practices were executed in the SOE, and those that were practiced, were minimally executed. The findings reveal that the corporate process management phase was not practiced and no BPM foundation was laid, as suggested by the models studied. BPM was driven by the ICT team, which acted as change agents, rather than top management. BPM was not incorporated into the organisational strategy. The findings also reveal that there was no process architecture in place; instead, the SOE focused mostly on prioritising the automation of certain processes, such as the finance and procurement processes. Despite incremental improvements achieved through automating the billing and invoice approval processes, the absence of a formal change management plan suggests a lack of strategic alignment and organisational readiness for a BPM project. The SOE employed a BPM improvement approach that focused on improving existing processes rather than redesigning them. Lastly, in terms of BPM practices, the process monitoring and control practices were lacking, hindering insights into conformance and performance.

This paper provides a descriptive contribution to BPM practices in SOEs, an understudied area. This study identified what worked and what did not in this case. There appears to be a culture (in how things are done) that impedes the full execution of a BPM project, and this warrants further exploration. Future research needs to explore the role of culture in BPM projects.

In addition, consolidating the three literature models offers a more comprehensive framework to BPM execution and can guide other enterprises to execute BPM pro-

jects. There were some limitations in this study: it utilised only one case and interviewed only 15 participants. Also, only three BPM lifecycle models were considered; it is possible that other models could potentially introduce additional practices.

Acknowledgments. The author extends her sincere gratitude to her research supervisor for the invaluable guidance and unwavering support throughout her academic journey.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

1. Nyatumba, M., Poore, R.: Failure to implement a turnaround strategy at South African Airways: Reflections from strategic players. *Development Southern Africa*, 40(1), pp. 76–90. (2021). doi:10.1080/0376835X.2021.1965865
2. Hammer, M.: What is business process management? In: vom Brocke, J., Rosemann, M Handbook on business process management 1. *International Handbooks on Information Systems* (1st ed.). pp.3-16. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg. (2015). doi:10.1007/978-3-642-45100-3_1
3. vom Brocke, J., Rosemann, M.: *Handbook on Business Process Management 2. Strategic alignment, governance, people and culture* (2nd ed.). Springer Berlin, Heidelberg. (2015). doi:10.1007/978-3-642-45103-4
4. Dumas, M., La Rosa, M., Mendling, J., Reijers, H. A.: *Fundamentals of Business Process Management*. (2nd ed). Springer. (2013). doi:10.1007/978-3-662-56509-4
5. Taylor, F. W.: *The Principles of Scientific Management*. Harper and Brothers. New York and London. (1911)
6. Becker, J., Rosemann, M., Röglinger, M., zur Muehlen, M.: Business Process Management - An introduction to the special focus issue. *Business and Information Systems Engineering*. 4(5), pp. 227-228. (2012). doi:10.1007/S12599-012-0228-2
7. Annisa, L. H., Mahendrawathi, E.: Impact of alignment between social media and business processes on SMEs' business process performance: A conceptual model. *Procedia Computer Science*. (2019). 161, pp. 1106-1113. doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2019.11.222
8. Bi, R.: The Impact of IT-Business Alignment on SME Performance: The Mediating Effects of Strategic Collaboration, Coordination, and Responsiveness. *Electronic Journal of Information Systems Evaluation* 23(1), pp. 112-125 (2020)
9. OECD Homepage, <https://oecd.org/corporate/state-owned-enterprises-as-global-competitors-9789264262096-en.htm>, last accessed 2026/02/01
10. Wolfswinkel, J.F, Furtmueller, E., Wilderom, C.P.: Using grounded theory as a method for rigorously reviewing literature. *European Journal of Information Systems* 22(1), pp. 45-55 (2013)
11. Ubaid, A.M., Dweiri, F.T.: Business process management (BPM): terminologies and methodologies unified. *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management* 11(6), 1046-1064. (2022)
12. Morias, R. M. D., Kazan, S., Pádua, S. I. D. D., Costa, A. L.: An analysis of BPM lifecycles from a literature review to framework proposal. *Business Process Management Journal* 20(3), 412-432. (2014)
13. Kosieradzka, A., Rostek, K.: The Multifaceted Character of Process Management in Organisations. In: *Process Management and Organisational Process Maturity: economic and non-economic organisations*. pp.1-33. Springer, (2021)

14. Taymouri, F., Rosa, M. L., Dumas, M., Maggi, F. M.: Business Process Variant Analysis: Survey and Classification. *Knowledge-Based Systems*. Elsevier. 211, pp.106557. (2021). doi: 10.1016/j.knosys.2020.106557
15. Reijers, H. A., van Wijk, S., Mutschler, B., Leurs, M.: BPM in Practice: Who Is Doing What? In international conference on business process management. pp.45-60. Springer, Heidelberg. (2010)
16. Harmon, P. *Business Process Change: A Business Process Management Guide for Managers and Process Professionals*. (3rd ed.). Elsevier. (2014)
17. DPSA.: 2016 Operations Management Framework. The DPSA Administration. (2016). <https://www.dpsa.gov.za/dpsa2g/documents/omf/Operations%20management%20framework1.pdf>. Last accessed 2026/01/16
18. Saunders, N. K., Lewis, P., Thornhill, A.: *Research methods for business students* (8th ed.). Harlow: Pearson. (2019).
19. Dubois, A., Gadde, L.: Systematic Combining: An Abductive Approach to Case Research. *Journal of Business Research* **55**(7), 553-560 (2022)
20. Khambule, I.: State Institutions and Development in South Africa: The Case of Two State-Owned Enterprises. *17*(1), pp. 63-79. *Insight on Africa*. (2025)
21. Chitiga, M., Henseler, M., Mabugu, R., Maisonnave, H.: The implications of deteriorating state-owned enterprise performance on the South African economy. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*, **93**(3). pp.731-754. (2021)
22. Chinomona, E. C., Nematatani, P., Ntshingila, L.: Optimising supply chain effectiveness among state-owned enterprises in South Africa. *Journal of Transport and Supply Chain Management*, **17**. 1-8. (2023).
23. Charmaz, K.: *Constructing Grounded Theory: A Practical Guide through Qualitative Analysis*. Sage. (2006)
24. Jackson, K., Bazeley, P.: *Qualitative data analysis with NVivo*. SAGE Publications. pp. 1-376. (2019)